

Administrators' Personnel Management Practices and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area, Rivers State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between administrators' personnel management practices and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population and sample size of the study was 204 consisting of 8 principals and 196 teachers from the eight public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State which infers a census study. Two questionnaire instruments titled "Administrator's Personnel Management Practices Questionnaire" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts, Two from Educational Management and One in Measurement and Evaluation. Test re-test method and Cronbach Alpha were used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded reliability indexes of 0.94, 0.87, 0.76 and 0.84. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) while the t-test transformation was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The finding revealed that there was a high and positive relationship between administrator's personnel management practices such as performance appraisal, instructional supervision, in-service training and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo local government area in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Oyigbo Local Government Area, under its legislative arm, in conjunction with school leaders should ensure that teachers are encouraged in their performance to avoid whatever factors that would discourage them from their duties and teachers Oyigbo Local Government Area in Rivers State should demonstrate competence in instructional supervision to teachers motivates them to be diligent in their jobs.

Keywords: Administrators, Personnel Management Practices, Appraisal, Instructional Supervision, in-service training, Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

The world is no longer what it used to be, it is changing faster and the world of economics, business and academy is changing alongside with it. All educational success rest on its personnel, that is why there is a growing universal awareness that personnel motivation is a prerequisite for the survival of any educational system, be it in the public or private sector of the economy. Thus Administration is constantly confronted with the task of having diagnose the various needs of the personnel so as to merge them into the educational needs. According to Sergey, Olga, and Igor (2020), Personnel management is one of the most important and challenging functions of the educational system. It is that which deals with the managerial functions of estimating and classifying human resource requirements for meeting organizational goals through people at work and their relationships with each other.

According to Bart and Alain (2019), Educational management is the process of bringing men and materials together in education for effective and functional teaching and learning in the school system. Management fulfills such demands by implementing policies linked to organizing, allocating, harnessing

human and material resources within the school system in order to achieve the stated objectives. Frederick and Allan (2021) defined school educational administration as a process primarily concerned with creating, maintaining and coordinating the resources and energy within an educational institution for the purpose of achieving predetermined goals.

In line with the above, Robert (2017) asserted that, personnel management acts as the wheel of progress in the realization of educational goals and objectives. It means that, without an effective personnel management, an organization may find it difficult to attain its set goals and objectives, it must seek to gain the co-operation of the personnel working under it. It is clear that personnel management is challenging in every organization but far more challenging in educational institutions. This is because most of the activities in education deal with human beings, Moez and Nicolas (2018) stated that of all tools in management; man, machine material and money, without any iota of doubt, the most important is man. Man is the only animate instrument that is capable of achieving Material, Machine, and money, Aja and Okorie 2018), perceived personnel management as an

important management function concerned with obtaining, developing and motivating the human resources required by an organization(school) to achieve its goals and objectives.

According to Elise, Anne and Lindsey (2015) was of the view that well managed teachers will always look for better ways to do their teaching. It is a known fact that, no educational institution can achieve its objectives without taking good care of competent and dedicated teachers. Additionally, prompt application of personnel management practices, has an important and influential impact on the teachers' job performance. Therefore, acquiring teacher's services, developing their skills, motivating them to higher levels of job performance and ensuring that they continue to maintain their commitment to the school system are essential to achieving educational goals.

Job performance according to Afshin, Hooshanf, and Esmail (2020) is a measure of how workers effectively combine and use resources in order to accomplish specific and desirable result of the educational system. In the researcher's opinion, teachers' job performance is the ability of the teacher to achieve its set goals in his assigned responsibility within the educational system. Dandan and Willibald (2019) projected the following benefits of an effective job performance.

1. Strengthening the general economic foundation of workers.
2. Improvement in working and living conditions.
3. Higher earnings.
4. Increased output or services at less resource.

According to Van-Dat (2015) acknowledged that, the context of school environment has changed tremendously such that the styles should change too. Personnel management practices can be achieved through the adoption of these management Practices: performance appraisal, instructional supervision, in-service training, and participation in decision making, hence any teacher that enjoys the influence of the above named practices may give all his best in discharging his/her duties because he would derive the satisfaction of being a teacher. Teachers' professional commitment is a very important factor in the educational system, especially when there is timely appraisal. Staff appraisal is an important technique that can be used by any educational administrators' if the school really wants to achieve its set objective. Putu, Ketut and Ernawati (2019) provides that; Staff appraisal is the assessment of the performance of an individual in relation to the

objectives, outputs, and targets of a job over a given period of time. The sole aim of performance appraisal is to monitor the employees work progress in order to improve productivity and also enhance promotion.

Instructional supervision in contemporary Nigeria, according to Paul, David and John (2016), is the process of enhancing the professional growth of the teachers, the curriculum and improving the techniques of teaching in the classroom through democratic interaction between the teacher and the supervisor. In-service training is one of the staff development programs which act as a catalyst for teachers' effectiveness. It is an important means of updating teachers' skills and knowledge for improving instruction and learning. Teachers needs to improve with greater commitment in school based decisions to provide leadership and effectiveness as people respond best when given freedom of action, because participation in decision-making affects their sense of empowerment. This will make the teachers to have a sense of commitment that may translate not only to improved performance but also to the attainment of the much desired goals of education particularly at the senior secondary schools.

Teachers in public senior secondary schools could perform effectively and efficiently to achieve educational goals when the administrators carry out performance appraisal, organize in-service training, carryout instructional supervision and also allow them to participate in decision making. It is against this background the researcher seek-to investigate educational administrators' personnel management practices and teachers job performance in public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The success of any level of education is hinged on the competency of school principals in their management practices. The problem of ineffective management by senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area in Rivers State is a common practice nowadays. Teachers of public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area in Rivers State do their jobs with a lot of laxity and this has affected the effectiveness and efficiency of their jobs.

Due to the absence of suitable Administrators' management practices in the public senior secondary schools, Teachers do not give in their best in their teaching job and it has affected both parents and students thereby making them rely more now on examination

malpractice; currently in Rivers State research has it that thirty- three senior secondary schools have been banned from presenting candidates for the West African Secondary School Certificate Examination, WASSCE over their involvement in examination malpractices in the 2020/2021 West African Secondary School Certificate Examination in Rivers State. Some of the schools include: Sit-up international school, Oyigboand Rich- Model Secondary school, Oyigbo etc.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine administrators' personnel management practices and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study tend to:

1. Determine the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.
3. Determine the relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed:

1. What is the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised and tested for the study @ 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

2. There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a Correlational research design. The area of the study is Oyigbo Local Government Area. The population of the study is (204) which comprises of eight (8) principals and one hundred and ninety - six (196) teachers from the eight (8) public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area. The total population was used as the sample size since the population is manageable. Instruments for data collections are questionnaires tagged "Administrator's Personnel Management Practices Questionnaire (APMPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). Three experts validated the instruments, two from educational management and one from measurement and evaluation. To establish the reliability of the instruments used the Cronbach Alpha method was adopted and reliability indexes of 0.94, 0.87, 0.76 and 0.84. Was obtained. Two research assistance helped the researcher in distributing the copies of the questionnaire after being guided. The 204 copies of the questionnaire administered were all retrieved at 100% rate and it was considered encouraging and acceptable. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). This was done based on the value and direction of the correlation viz; 0.1 – 0.4 was counted as "low correlation", 0.5 denotes "moderate correlation" while 0.6 – 1.0 denotes "high correlation". While the t-test transformation was used to test the null hypotheses. Where the calculated t-transformation value was less than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted and rejected when the calculated t-transformation value was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 .

RESULTS

Research Question 1: Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in

public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship Between Performance Appraisal and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

		Performance Appraisal	Teachers’ Job Performance	Level of Correlation
Performance Appraisal	Pearson Correlation	1	.661**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	204	204	High and
Teachers’ Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	.661**	1	Positive
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		Relationship
	N	204	204	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 1 for research question 1 showed the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State. The result on Table 1 revealed that responses to questionnaire items 1-5 for performance appraisal and questionnaire items 1-15 for teachers’ job performance had correlation value of .661**. This implies that there is a high and positive

relationship between performance appraisal and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 2: Research Question 2: What is the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area in Rivers State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship Between Instructional Supervision and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

		Instructional Supervision	Teachers’ Job Performance	Level of Correlation
Instructional Supervision	Pearson Correlation	1	.721**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	204	204	High and
Teachers’ Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	.721**	1	Positive
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		Relationship
	N	204	204	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 for research question 2 showed the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State. The result on Table 2 revealed that responses to questionnaire items 6-10 for instructional supervision and questionnaire items 1-15 for teachers' job performance had correlation value of

.721^{**}. This implied that there is a high and positive relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State?

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship Between In-Service Training and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

		In-Service Training	Teachers' Job Performance	Level of Correlation
In-Service Training	Pearson Correlation	1	.881 ^{**}	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	204	204	High and
Teachers' Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	.881 ^{**}	1	Positive
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		Relationship
	N	204	204	

^{**}. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 for research question 3 showed the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on the relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State. The result on Table 3 revealed that responses to questionnaire items 11-15 for in-service training and questionnaire items 1-15 for teachers' job performance had correlation value of .881^{**}. This implied that there is a high and positive

relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State

Table 4 Summary of t-Test Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Performance Appraisal and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-cal.	t-crit.	α	Decision
Performance Appraisal	204			21.50			
		202	.661 ^{**}		±1.96	0.05	Ho ₁ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Teachers' Job Performance	204						

Table 4 showed the t-test transformation summary on the significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary

schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The result on Table 4 revealed that t-calculated value of 21.50 was greater than the t-critical value of

± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 202 degree of freedom. Since the t-calculated value of 21.50 was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative upheld which

states that there is a significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of t-Test Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Instructional Supervision and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-cal.	t-crit.	α	Decision
Instructional Supervision	204						
		202	.721**	19.71	± 1.96	0.05	Ho ₂ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Teachers' Job Performance	204						

Table 5 showed the t-test transformation summary on the significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The result on Table 5 revealed that t-calculated value of 19.71 was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 202 degree of freedom. Since the t-calculated value of 19.71 was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null

hypothesis was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 6 Summary of t-Test Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between In-Service Training and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-cal.	t-crit.	α	Decision
In-Service Training	204						
		202	.881**	16.13	± 1.96	0.05	Ho ₃ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Teachers' Job Performance	204						

Table 6 showed the t-test transformation summary on the significant relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State. The result on Table 6 revealed that t-calculated value of 16.13

was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 202 degree of freedom. Since the t-calculated value of 16.13 was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant

relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools of Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Discussion of the Findings

Relationship Between Performance Appraisal and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

The findings obtained on research question 1 on Table 1 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State with 'r' as .661**. Hypothesis 1 on Table 4 showed that there was a significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State with t-test transformation value of 21.50 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding is in agreement with Amie-Ogan (2015) who opined that performance appraisal is a process of trying to find out how well an employee has fared or performed over a period of time. Her view recognizes that this approach helps the human resource management of the educational sector to identify the areas teachers find challenging in the process of teaching and mapping out strategies on how to train them.

Relationship Between Instructional Supervision and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

The findings obtained on research question 2 on Table 2 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area in Rivers State with 'r' as .721**. Hypothesis 2 on Table 5 showed that there was a significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area in Rivers State with t-test transformation value of 19.71 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding is in line with Ikegbusi (2014) who argued that, in order to ensure that teachers are highly disciplined and their high productivity achieved in the education sector, apart from staff development will also include strengthening supervision to ensure work commitment is guaranteed and enhanced.

Relationship Between In-Service Training and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State.

The findings obtained on research question 3 on Table 3 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State with 'r' as .881**. Hypothesis 3 on Table 6 showed that there was a significant relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Area of Rivers State with t-test transformation value of 16.13 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding corroborates with Nwabueze (2010) who noted that, training is intended to assist teachers within the school to acquire relevant, desirable and expertise knowledge, skills, ideas and competencies that will enable them to perform effectively and efficiently in achieving the goals of the school.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the study have revealed a very significant relationship between administrator's personnel management practices and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo Local Government Area in Rivers State, Nigeria. Hence, the study concluded that it is safe to say that leaders of different educational institutions, particularly public senior secondary schools should endeavour to synergize their efforts to consciously make educational reforms that will promote personnel management practices, thereby bringing about better teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Oyigbo local government area in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Oyigbo Local Government Area, under its legislative arm, in conjunction with school leaders should ensure that teachers are encouraged in their performance, to avoid whatever factors that would discourage them from their duties.
2. The Oyigbo Local Government Area in Rivers State should demonstrate competence in

- instructional supervision to teachers motivates them to be diligent in their jobs.
3. The Oyigbo Local Government Area in Rivers State should as much as possible always ensure that senior secondary school teachers are given in-service training as a form of encouragement to the teachers.

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